

Beyond Skills-Cycling: A Three-Phase Framework for Cognitive Progression in KS2 Reading Comprehension

Abstract

This paper proposes a new, three-phase approach to teaching reading in Key Stage 2 by synthesising and utilising existing research. The framework aims to link existing practice in UK primary schools to evidence, research, and Ofsted recommendations. Additionally, it aims to offer a practical and effective alternative to reading schemes which elicit surface-level comprehension and fail to consider fluency, cognitive science and metacognition. The approach splits a six-week unit into three phases. The first phase focuses on building the textbase by teaching vocabulary, retrieval, and instruction of all fluency skills to support and display comprehension. Phase 2 focuses on eliciting a deeper understanding of the text by analysing authorial intent and teaching inferential thinking. The paper will explain how effective teaching of both of these domains is only possible with the textbase secured in Phase 1. Phase 3 (synthesis and application) takes place when all material in the text has been met, focusing on synthesising all learning in the unit, exploring thematic inference, analysing character arcs, writing about the whole text and writing ‘from the text’ in the style of the author. The paper also outlines why this approach is preferred to several existing schools of reading teaching in KS2 and demonstrates how pupils achieve a more sustainable comprehension, which is transferable to other texts. As a whole, the framework reflects a cognitive progression in reading comprehension. Pupils first construct a text base which represents the literal propositions of a text (Kintsch, 1998). Once the foundation is secure, they begin constructing a situational model through inferential thinking about characters, events and authorial choice. Finally, pupils synthesise meaning across a text, engaging in thematic interpretation and extended response.

Introduction

Throughout primary schools in the UK, there are a vast number of approaches to teaching reading. Having worked in several schools during my early career, I have witnessed this firsthand and have noted a lack of consensus around approaches to the subject, which highly contrasts with Mathematics or writing, where, in general, several schemes dominate and are informed by a wealth of research and pedagogy.

While the VIPERS approach of teaching reading as discrete, standalone skills in isolation seems to be acknowledged as limited and not representative of a child’s genuine encounter with a text, the traces of it still linger in many schools without teachers understanding where this approach is incomplete. This can often present as the teaching of an isolated comprehension skill for the duration of the week without any explanation of why each skill is being taught. Alternatively, some schools take the approach of cycling through skills on a day-to-day basis and attempting to ‘tick off’ all domains by the end of a week before moving on to a new text. Although this approach is attractive in its capacity for allowing teachers to assess skills and update assessment tools on a regular basis, there are several fundamental flaws. While the EEF has demonstrated that the ‘explicit teaching of individual comprehension skills improves literacy’ (EEF, 2021), it also notes that while initially these skills may be taught in isolation, they must be applied to a range of activities and contexts. Using the National Curriculum, schools can quickly and

effectively identify the key domains that need to be taught in order for children to achieve comprehension of a text; however, many schools and teachers lack a clear framework that enables these domains to be integrated in a meaningful text-led way that teaches pupils to be effective independent readers.

The approach that I will outline in this article considers, at its core, that these domains cannot be taught as stand-alone skills which rotate Willingham (2017) arbitrarily and that the cycling of skills as a means of ticking off assessment areas leads to weaker outcomes with children learning only to answer specific question types rather than developing a meaningful understanding of a text. Shanahan et al. (2010). Another fundamental flaw with the aforementioned approaches is that they do not allow pupils to build up the lexical and contextual framework, which they require to engage with a text at a deeper level using skills such as character inference and analysis of authorial intent. Woolley (2011) The approach which I am outlining is guided by the principle that pupils need to develop a strong text-base and lexical understanding in order to engage with crucial 'deepening understanding' skills.

By focusing on ticking off key comprehension skills, we overlook the foundational role of fluency, and in KS2, there is a chronic neglect of these skills and the viewpoint that fluency is an early reading skill that serves little purpose once children progress from KS1. This approach rejects this notion and reflects the fact that the explicit teaching and mastery of fluency skills in KS2 aids pupils' cognition and ability to comprehend a text. Rasinski (2004)

While it is clear that the teaching of reading comprehension is a fundamentally complex process (Willingham, 2009), there is a clear tension between the wealth of readily available research and the current practices, which can be seen in many UK primary schools today. This article outlines an approach which aims to bridge the gap between current research and current practice and provide teachers with an effective and understandable framework which incorporates a wealth of research and pedagogy into its foundation and structure. It achieves this by presenting a clear three-phase structure: Phase 1 serves as the foundation, building the text. Phase 2 focuses on deepening and building the situational model of the text, while Phase 3 focuses on application and synthesis.

Literature review

As teachers, we are beholden to the national curriculum, which presents reading as a simple series of isolated comprehension skills; therefore, it can be difficult to translate these statutory bullet points into a meaningful and effective pedagogy. With the framework we are given, it is clear why we often fall short. However, after experiencing much frustration with the lack of coherence and clarity in identifying best practice in reading, I was heartened to discover a vast pool of fantastic research and theory about how children read. By understanding this effectively, we can move away from ticking off assessment points arbitrarily and transition to a methodology which teaches children to become excellent readers.

This understanding begins with Kintsch's (1998) textbase and situation model, where Kintsch outlines that comprehension is a two-step process where the textbase is built first, this being the surface level meaning of the vocabulary, the factual content and the literal propositions that are offered. The textbase is followed by the establishment of the situational model, where the reader builds a mental model of the situation that is being described and a mental understanding of what

the text is about. This requires inferences to be made from background knowledge and a deeper understanding of the content read.

An understanding of Kintsch's view of reading comprehension is quickly met with the realisation that in our classrooms, we are not allowing children to fully establish a solid textbase from which they can draw inferences and develop a deeper understanding of the text. We cannot expect the children to develop their situational model of what they are reading if they have not been provided with the tools to achieve this – the key vocabulary, the background knowledge of place and time relevant to the text they are reading. Without a solid literal foundation, the inferential becomes unstable and can lead to wildly inaccurate responses to inference questions, owing simply to the fact that the child was not able to solidly establish the textbase and decode the context of what was read and therefore make guesses rather than accurately inferring.

Rasinski's (2004) research on the key role of fluency in a child's ability to comprehend a text is highly complementary to the research presented by Kintsch. Rasinski strengthens our understanding of the importance of fluency by teaching us that by developing control over 'surface level processing', children are able to free up cognitive capacity for comprehension. By neglecting these foundational skills, we widen the fluency gap for a large number of children who, in turn, are expending precious cognitive resources on decoding a text rather than truly understanding it. Additionally, Rasinski provides us with a progression of fluency skills and establishes an order in which pupils can apply fluency skills throughout a reading unit. By first consolidating accuracy, pupils are then able to read with automaticity, which is where brainpower can be spared for comprehension, before moving on to establishing prosodic skills such as phrasing and intonation, which reflect a text's meaning and also serve as the crucial tool that enables children to create meaning as they read. This progression is as fundamental in Year 6, where pupils benefit from additional cognitive capacity to understand the meaning of a complex text, as it is in Reception, where children are attempting to comprehend a text following a fluency read.

Kintsch and Rasinski's research is supported by Cain and Oakhill (2007), who present the notion that far from being a single skill, comprehension is a complex "orchestration" of many processes which coexist and function simultaneously. Cain and Oakhill outline that while readers may be able to decode words effectively, they can still experience great difficulty in achieving comprehension of a text. They discovered that readers with this profile had a critical lack of vocabulary, supporting the concept that a lack of comprehension can be attributed to a lack of knowledge and further reveals the importance of constructing a comprehensive and secure textbase before attempting to analyse the text at a deeper level.

Furthermore, the crucial role of metacognition is raised by Cain and Oakhill, who emphasise that a child's ability to independently monitor their own comprehension of what they have read separates more skilled readers and better outcomes from less skilled readers and poorer results. By recognising when concepts do not align or where ideas are in tension with one another, pupils are able to identify the need to apply repair strategies to help make sense of the text. However, the EEF (2025) emphasises that these metacognition skills must be taught explicitly and in a guided manner for pupils to be able to use them and integrate them within their toolkit as effective readers. In our classrooms, this can be incorporated in an engaging manner through explicit naming of metacognitive skills such as clarifying, questioning and monitoring for understanding and by applying these strategies, thinking aloud during modelled reads.

If we understand the foundation of a textbase as a crucial step in our pupils' ability to read and understand what they read, then the work of Beck et al (2002) on vocabulary plays a crucial role. Beck et al provide a vital framework from which we can organise our lexical instruction rather than presenting and teaching a random pick of words. This work is widely understood and utilised within primary education; however, further refinement and application within a structured framework are necessary within reading lessons. Tier 1 words constitute the high-frequency everyday vocabulary that children are comfortable with and expend less cognitive capacity comprehending. Tier 3 vocabulary is the subject-specific vocabulary that is limited to specific domains. Tier 2 vocabulary must be our primary focus in our approach to reading. While not subject-specific, this academic and transferable vocabulary is extremely useful for children to have a solid understanding of. While the teaching of tier 3 vocabulary is necessary for our children to understand a text, these words are less frequent, and tier 2 vocabulary is what will enable our pupils to transfer their knowledge and word-reading skills intertextually. While this is understood by many teachers, our delivery often falls short. Beck et al highlight that pupils require between 4 and 14 encounters with a word before they can internalise and comprehend it. This leads us to ensure that taught words are continually revisited and accessed in a multitude of ways – children should have sufficient opportunity to use these newly taught words orally in a structured manner, in addition to their reading of them. Furthermore, the teaching of these words must also be deliberate and follow a routine which supports effective internalisation and synthesis. Beck et al (2013) highlight the need for pupils to view the “portability” of tier 2 vocabulary, and in a lesson, this means allowing pupils to hear and use the word in several different contexts. Furthermore, on revealing a word, it is helpful for it to be visualised using an image or gesture, contextualised and explained in a pupil-friendly way. Simply finding and reading a word in the dictionary is not sufficient, as these explanations are often too abstract for pupils.

The theory behind the importance of continual and repeated encounters with a new word is also supported by the work of Cervetti and Hiebert (2015), who demonstrate that a knowledge-building curriculum which focuses on fewer texts in a deeper manner leads to stronger comprehension gains rather than frequent topic switching. In the latter case, pupils are not given sufficient encounters with new words to embed them. The works of both Cervetti and Hiebert and Beck et al further strengthen and highlight the importance of establishing a secure textbase, Kintsch (1998), which enables pupils to then begin to construct a situational model on firm foundations.

The Three-Phase approach

The convergence of this research led me to a key insight: reading is not a simple list of skills which can be selected and taught according to the assessment requirements of schools and teachers. While we can ensure curriculum coverage in this way, these concepts are explored at a surface level and cannot function without following a sequential model, which nurtures the inherent sequence of how pupils establish a textbase and move towards the inferential and deeper understanding of a text, Kintsch (1998). Rasinski (2004) also demonstrates that fluency must progress sequentially for maximum comprehension gains, moving from accuracy to automaticity and onto prosody. This orchestration of processes outlined by Cain and Oakhill (2007) develops in a clear, logical hierarchy which must be respected in order to help our pupils to become better, effective readers. It is vital to emphasise that my proposed framework does not act as a new

sequence of individual skills and processes. It is not the case that by following individual skills in the correct order, our pupils will become excellent readers.

We cannot arbitrarily look at skills in isolation for a given amount of time before moving on to the next, even if we have sequenced them according to research and logic. Two weeks of vocabulary instruction followed by two weeks of inference and then authorial intent is ineffective and remains an arbitrary proposition.

For practical purposes, given the realities of half-termly planning and school calendars, I have provided boundaries between phases; however, these are emergent rather than inherent. They are not fixed. Each process and skill should be woven into each phase in a seamless and naturally recurring manner. For example, fluency teaching begins immediately in Phase 1 but continues into Phases 2 and 3. Inference is foregrounded in Phase 2, but smaller opportunities for inferential thinking arise in Phase 1. In Phase 3, inference continues to develop.

This proposal is not a new checklist that we can blindly follow and expect results. The Phase schedule is an organisational tool, not a reflection of a clear-cut internal development of comprehension which follows a neat pattern. Comprehension in a child's mind is complex, messy and recursive.

Having said this, the progression of domains and metacognitive strategies, which I will outline have been carefully developed based on all of the research detailed here. They become a genuinely valuable pedagogy when domains which have been taught are carefully interleaved throughout the three phases and the domains and metacognitive strategies are taught in a way which is led by the text and the content explored.

Phase 1

The first phase of this framework draws largely on the work of Kintsch (1998), Rasinski (2004), Cain and Oakhill (2007) and Beck et al. (2012,2013). The primary objectives of this phase are to build an extremely solid textbase and to develop fluency skills within the context of the text to free up cognition for the deeper thinking which is more prevalent in Phase 2. Phase 1 treats fluency as foundational rather than assuming it is already secure. The domains that are primarily taught here are vocabulary and retrieval. Vocabulary is the key ingredient that underpins and precedes all other domains to be taught. It is exercised continually and deliberately throughout Phase 1. Nagy and Scott (2000) demonstrate that tier 2 language is rarely acquired incidentally and therefore the process here must be deliberate and sustained. For example, pupils reading a text about ancient Pompeii cannot explain the impact of the author's choice to use 'catastrophe' if they do not have a secure understanding of the word's meaning and have not used it and seen it in different contexts. Whilst teaching 'Escape from Pompeii' using the three-phase structure, we came across this very word. I introduced it using a routine adapted from Beck's research. We began by saying the word together multiple times, I then showed the image from the text of the volcanic eruption and explained the word in child-friendly terms: "a terrible disaster that causes great damage or suffering." We then explored this word in a different context, discussing how losing a jumper on the playground is not a catastrophe, but an erupting volcano destroying a city is. This enabled us to connect the meaning of the word with the textbase and also the pupils' own lives. The pupils continued to encounter this word throughout the unit as I included it in retrieval starters, discussion prompts and as a result, the pupils had encountered it over seven times, which

aligns with Beck's recommendation. I noticed that pupils would volunteer this word willingly in their own responses to other tasks and prompts and were able to apply it accurately to their own arguments.

Retrieval and recording (NC2B) acts as the anchor which strengthens the textbase. This is comprehension in its most basic form – the identification of literal facts. If pupils are able to retrieve information on the who, what, where and when, they are actively displaying that they are comprehending the text. Furthermore, Kintsch emphasises that inferential thinking cannot be applied if pupils cannot recall the content of the text. Retrieval, therefore, is an invaluable tool in Phase 1, where the textbase is still being constructed and nurtured. Children must be able to identify the who, where, when and what of the text so that they can engage more deeply with it later, without the fundamental textbase being shaken. Additionally, without the mastery of these skills, pupils are not able to navigate the text by scanning and quickly locating vital information. (Duke & Pearson, 2002) Lacking this, pupils will struggle later on to provide evidence to support their assertions in the 'deepening' phase of the framework. An example of a task which not only exercises retrieval in a text-led way, but also introduces the importance of finding evidence to support pupil assertions is the following: *Oracy exercise about the Forum. In pairs, pupils use the following stems.*

In the forum people would _____, I know this because the text says _____.

Here, pupils learn to paraphrase and also to quickly retrieve evidence to support their initial claims. This oral exercise also encourages the metacognitive technique of clarifying. Pupils identify from memory what happens in the forum and then use the text to clarify and evidence their understanding. This task is then formalised as a written response to consolidate learning. The reason that this activity is text-led and avoids the pitfall of listing endless retrieval questions is that the forum is central to the page. It is vital that pupils understand how the forum functions and how it is of central importance to an ancient Roman city – this is essential in establishing a solid text base. This activity also incorporates and interleaves vocabulary instruction as the class met the term 'forum' days prior, following the routine outlined in this paper, displaying how domains should appear in a recursive and non-linear manner within each phase to replicate internal comprehension.

The EEF emphasises the value of teaching Metacognition strategies explicitly. ((EEF, 2025)) Pupils must know when they do not understand the text, and they must understand how to fix it. Pupils will not effectively develop these skills incidentally, and therefore, in Phase 1, these skills are explicitly taught, modelled and applied alongside key reading and fluency domains. In Phase 1, Monitoring is at the forefront of this as pupils are taught to recognise where their understanding 'clicks' or 'clunks' (Klinger & Vaughn, 1998). This is heavily scaffolded in the initial part of Phase 1 and then slowly internalised and made more independent as we approach Phase 2. (EEF, 2018). Pupils should be taught what to do when their understanding clunks, and teachers should model rereading, reading around and looking for 'anchor words' that they understand and will help contextualise the text, which is 'clunking'. The role of the teacher is vital here, and the 'think-aloud' when modelling a read helps pupils to explicitly see what happens when something is not understood and what happens to rectify this.

Another vital aspect of Phase 1 (which then continues consistently throughout the framework) is purposeful retrieval activities as an opener for each lesson. It is important to differentiate here between retrieval: the reading domain NC2B (finding key information in a text) and retrieval: The spaced retrieval of previous learning (pulling memory out of the brain). I will now discuss the latter and how it is utilised within this framework. Roediger and Karpicke (2006) emphasise that retrieval strengthens memory more than re-reading and that the act of testing consolidates what has been read. This is also invaluable in consolidating the text base and securing pupils' knowledge of the context. The retrieval activities are included on a daily basis as a brief five-minute activity, as Kornell & Bjork (2008) emphasise that spaced retrieval is far more effective in strengthening memory than one burst of retrieval at the end of a unit. This practice is widely acknowledged in primary schools; however, tasks can often be meaningless and low impact (the typical example of “tell your partner what you remember about yesterday’s learning”). This retrieval is low quality and less impactful – pupils are not being directed to what they are supposed to be extracting from their memory. The retrieval activities I have drawn upon in this framework are incredibly varied and specific. In a 6-week unit, up to 15 different varieties of retrieval activities can be included. This is a deliberate decision; it is not the act of picking and choosing random activities because they appear fun. Agarwal and Bain (2019) emphasise that retrieval in varied formats is effective as it develops pupils’ flexible recall; they are not just learning to answer questions in one specific way. Examples could be sketching a diagram and labelling with key vocabulary words from previous lessons, A triangle debate about a key event with one pupil summarising and feeding back to the class or sequencing key events from a previous page or event. Pupils are learning to engage with previous learning in a different form and can retrieve it in multiple contexts. Additionally, the inclusion of retrieval activities in Phase 1 goes hand in hand with the teaching of metacognitive strategies and the two are deeply interwoven. Retrieval creates a very clear image in the child’s mind of what they know and what they do not (Cain & Oakhill, 2007).

Phase 2

The primary aims of this phase are to develop inferential and analytical thinking, and it requires a focus on the assumption that pupils have a secure textbase with which to develop their situational model. This is not to say that all content must be explored in Phase 1. Far from it, new pages are met continuously in Phase 2; however, the deliberate period of building the textbase is essential (the temporal context, the geographical context and a large bank of tier 2/3 words will already be committed to the long-term memory if Phase 1 has been delivered accurately). This means that when pupils encounter a new page, they already have a strong armoury of context and relevant vocabulary to quickly tackle new material with – they have established a strong schema, and they have a strong mental framework to assimilate new information (Anderson & Pearson, 1984). This leads to the freeing of cognitive capacity with which to tackle the deeper questions, and the intrinsic cognitive load of the new pages is reduced as the content of the new pages builds on existing knowledge (Sweller, 1988).

However, teacher judgement is vital; if there is a page which has an overwhelming proportion of novel themes, vocabulary and ideas, then a textbase needs to be established. This strengthens the argument made at the start of this paper that processes should not be followed arbitrarily. In the case mentioned above, a microcosm of phases 1 and 2 can be applied over a two-day period. A highly complex and thematically novel page can be read once to establish an understanding of the new vocabulary and the context, and then the next day the same page is utilised to explore

the inferential. This strategy draws directly from Kintsch's model and does not disrupt the aims of Phase 2.

In order to approach inference and authorial intent in a way which builds on comprehension skills hierarchically, local inference should be explored first – 'why is something happening'. Following this character inference should be explored – looking at character motivation directly builds on local inference and progresses the skill in an incremental step. Cain and Oakhill (2007) argue that local inferences (character motivations, etc.) have a lower cognitive demand and develop prior to global inferences, where whole-text themes are explored. This led me to introduce discussion on themes only lightly towards the end of Phase 2, before approaching it in a more formal way in Phase 3, where the pupils synthesise their full understanding of the text. Cross-page inference can also be developed towards the end of Phase 2, as this requires a higher cognitive demand than single-page inference. An example of an independent task early on in Phase 2, which I applied to my unit, is a simple sentence frame activity. In 'Escape from Pompeii', two characters respond in very different ways to initial signs of the eruption. This point is elicited in oracy activities with the sentence stems. *I think _____ feels _____ because the text says " _____ ".*

Not only does this ensure that pupils take an active role in selecting the character they wish to evaluate, but it also forces them to retrieve key evidence from the text to support their assertions. This simple character inference provides a model and begins working on the skills needed to engage with global inference later on.

Authorial intent, which appears in the National Curriculum as NC2F, is crucial in deepening a pupil's understanding of a text. By understanding why an author has made certain choices, pupils are able to further explore what the text is about. Additionally, predictive inference should be included throughout Phase 2, as Duke and Pearson (2002) express that prediction develops active reading and metacognitive awareness, which we have already explored, leading to stronger comprehension.

The role of fluency is still vital throughout Phase 2. Although there is less explicit instruction in this period of the framework, the fluency skills from accuracy to automaticity to the prosodic should be deeply embedded within the unit of work and the children's approach to reading new material. (Rasinski 2004) Fluency skills should be explicitly discussed prior to, during and after modelled reads, choral and echo reads, and partner reads. Constant feedback should be offered to pupils on their use of prosodic skills.

Retrieval practice maintains the same philosophy as in phase one, with regular, short, spaced retrieval activities in a variety of task types, so that pupils are retrieving previous learning flexibly. Retrieval at this phase of the unit should act as a method of continually propping up the textbase and ensuring that the context and vocabulary knowledge is sustained so that pupils can continue to engage with deepening questions and then synthesis as the unit concludes.

During Phase 2, a proportion of the time should be spent completing a 'close read' of the page. Pupils benefit from direct modelling here and will be able to independently engage with deepening questions if they experience their teacher using evidence from the text to assert their own viewpoints. This is effective for all varieties of Phase 2 questioning, and pupils will begin to see that the skills required to apply a deeper analysis of the text are transferable. All independent

activities should be rooted in oracy discussions before pupils are expected to answer deepening questions on their own, as the EEF (2021) emphasises that critical thinking is advanced through high-quality discussion and written responses are scaffolded through oral rehearsal. Sentence stems are extremely beneficial here as they ensure that pupils are evidencing their assertions with direct material from the text. In this phase, pupils will look at character and emotional inference, linking the inferential to the textbase (Kintsch, 1998). They should analyse how form and structure contribute to the meaning of a passage, which enhances their analytical reading skills as outlined by Fisher and Frey (2012), and additionally, they should analyse how figurative language is used by the author to contribute towards meaning. In this case, the solid textbase and lexical understanding will allow pupils to distinguish between the literal and figurative.

An example which I applied in my Year 3 classroom of analysing how authorial choice over structure contributes to meaning is by undertaking a close read of the following passage. *'Quick — the harbour! Run! Just run!'* This passage describes two children responding to the eruption of Mount Vesuvius in 'Escape to Pompeii'. I have extracted the following text straight from my plan to provide a clear example of how dialogic teaching paves the way for pupils' written responses. *What is the author doing here? Why does this make the reader feel tense?'*

Class share. Build the understanding: sentence length mirrors emotional state and urgency. This class discussion is then followed by a structured partner read and discussion using the following stems: *'I could feel the tension when you read _____ because _____.'* This stem leads directly into the independent task where the discussion is formalised. The following stems are provided to pupils, *'When the author writes short sentences like _____, the reader feels _____ because _____.'*

(b) Using Stem 3: 'I think the most effective moment on this page is _____ because the author _____.'

Pupils must use one vocabulary word from Tuesday in their response. This scaffolding was critical in introducing authorial intent to pupils. They were directed to use evidence, and the sentence stem ensured that they engaged directly with the effect on the reader and, by extension, the intention of the author. Note how vocabulary practice is interleaved here by including the requirement that pupils utilise explicitly taught vocabulary in their responses. As the text base was secure, pupils were able to apply these words accurately and in the correct context. This lesson structure itself followed a pattern of I do, we do, you do (Pearson & Gallagher, 1983). This withdrawal of scaffolding supports the pupils to be accurate in their independent tasks.

Metacognition continues to play a crucial role in this process with a particular focus on how pupils ask themselves questions about the text to probe their understanding. Palinscar and Brown (1984) emphasise the value of this metacognitive strategy, and the process is interwoven with the questions that inference and authorial intent questions pose to the reader: the why.

Phase 3

The purpose of this final phase of each unit is to demonstrate that comprehension is secure and durable. Phase 3 attempts to move from teacher-guided practice to independent application and

synthesis of everything they have learnt about the text so far. By the time that Phase 3 begins, pupils have read the entire text and therefore are able to engage with multiple ideas from a variety of sections or pages. This approach reflects Kornell and Bjork's viewpoint that spacing and depth have a larger impact than focusing only on coverage. We are spending between one and two weeks analysing and unpicking what we have read.

In this phase, pupils will begin to synthesise their reading into summaries and sequence a character's journey from beginning to end, analysing changes or evolution as the text progresses. Children will be able to discuss the plot as a whole, which is possible due to the establishment of a strong textbase (Phase 1) and a strong situational model (Phase 2) (Kintsch, 1998). In this stage of the unit, pupils can begin looking at themes throughout the text in depth and discuss their effect on the reader. The practice of 'zooming out the lens' and taking a look at the text holistically is supported by Graham & Hebert (2010), who argue that meta-analysis of a whole text and extended written responses about a text deepen comprehension. The research proves, however, that this can only take place when deep reading and analysis have occurred, which this model supports as Phases 1 and 2 provide the in-depth understanding of the text from start to finish.

Phase 3 draws heavily on the work of Graham and Hebert (2010), who distinguish between writing about reading (analysis) and writing from reading, which is the act of applying the writer's techniques to the pupil's own writing. For example, writing a character description in the style of the author they are reading shows a deep understanding of authorial craft. This approach is supported by Fisher and Frey (2013), who say that pupils who read like writers – noticing writers' craft – comprehend more deeply. Similarly, Myhill (2012) explains that learning about grammatical structures in a highly contextualised environment is far more beneficial than decontextualised activities. This analysis of grammatical structures and their contribution to the meaning of the text is extremely contextualised in the model presented here, as it occurs in the final phase of the unit, where the textbase and the situational model are strong. Below, I have directly lifted from my planning the sequence of learning leading to the pupil's independent activity, following the 'writing from reading' approach. Note how all authorial techniques are discussed and modelled beforehand. On the day following this activity, another similar independent writing from reading activity is posed to the pupils with reduced scaffolding prior to their writing, in line with Pearson and Gallagher's guidance on scaffold reduction.

Display PowerPoint: the four technique terms as a checklist.

'Today your challenge is to tick as many of these as you can in your own writing.'

No extended discussion — move straight to shared writing.

3. Shared writing, (class paragraph) (10 min)

The teacher writes a short paragraph (3-4 sentences) in front of the class on the board or visualiser, thinking aloud throughout and asking pupils for contributions:

Sentence 1: set the scene — use figurative language. 'The sea churned like a restless animal beneath the dark sky.'

Sentence 2: use short sentences for tension. 'The captain listened. Something was wrong.'

Sentence 3: use a sensory detail — the children asleep, unaware. 'Below deck, Tranio and Livia slept, their faces grey with ash, their breathing shallow.'

Sentence 4: echo the technique of reader over character — 'They did not know that the winds had turned. They did not know that Pompeii was already gone.'

After each sentence, ask: 'What technique am I using here? What effect does it create?'

Read the paragraph aloud together — choral read.

4. Planning talk using stem 1 (2 min)

Pupils tell their partner: Stem 1 — what technique they will use and what effect they want.

30 seconds planning in books: 3 bullet point notes maximum.

5. Independent writing (10 min)

Pupils write their own 3-4 sentence description of the boat scene.

They may describe the same moment as the shared writing or choose a slightly different focus: the captain on deck, the sea pulling back, or Tranio and Livia waking.

Technique checklist visible on PowerPoint throughout.

Vocabulary bank visible on PowerPoint throughout.

No other support during these 10 minutes— pupils write responses in books.

This lesson is preceded by a lesson explicitly discussing figurative techniques and the effect they have on the reader – another crucial aspect of authorial intent.

Another distinct feature of Phase 3 is the gradual reduction of scaffolding, which reaches its pinnacle in this phase. In Phase 1, pupils are provided with independent tasks with structured scaffolding and sentence frames. In Phase 2, pupils' responses often use scaffolds which are more open and do not dictate responses but ensure that they are evidenced. This scaffold is dramatically reduced in Phase 3 and appears mainly in the form of task prompts. This deliberate, gradual release of responsibility (Pearson & Gallagher, 1983) serves to test whether comprehension is independent and the learning in Phases 2 and 3 is synthesised. Of course, pupils who require adaptation still receive scaffolding to support them in achieving the learning objective of each lesson. However, for pupils who are working securely at an age-related level, the ability to respond to the Phase 3 task effectively and with minimal scaffolding demonstrates that their textbase (Phase 1) is secure and their situational model (Phase 2) is well established.

Fluency instruction takes another key role in Phase 3, with performance reading acting as the culmination of the fluency progression, which I outlined in Phase 1. Rasinski (2004) emphasises that reading with prosody reflects and deepens a pupil's comprehension. Similarly, Worthy and Prater (2002) demonstrate that readers' theatre (performance reading) improves both fluency and comprehension.

Metacognition takes on a new importance here too as pupils begin to reflect on what they have learnt about the text and how their understanding has developed since they began reading in Phase 1. Not only this, pupils reflect not only on what they learned about the text but also on what they learned about reading itself. This approach is explicitly recommended in the EEF (2018), which states that readers should actively reflect on their learning processes as well as their learning outcomes.

All of these processes demonstrate that Phase 3 is not just a simple 'reflect and move on' end-of-unit activity but a sustained and cumulative analysis of the text itself and the pupil's learning. They make comparisons between themes, characters, and authorial choices, all of which lead to a deeper comprehension of the text (Cervetti and Hiebert, 2015).

In practice

I have explored the theory behind the model in great detail throughout the paper, and although I have provided several concrete examples of classroom practice throughout, I will now provide some clear examples of lesson outlines, domain, metacognitive and fluency progressions and explore, in practical terms, how each phase differs and builds from the previous.

Typical lesson progression

- Introduction to LO, fluency, metacognition and comprehension domains
- Retrieval practice
- Vocabulary instruction
- Modelled read with fluency focus
- Modelled read with metacognitive think-aloud.
- Choral / echo read
- Partner read with fluency focus.
- Oracy discussion on key reading domain – scaffolded
- Independent task
- Plenary and review

Progression of metacognition, fluency skills and comprehension domains in Phase 1

Comprehension

NC2a Vocabulary and NC2b retrieval interwoven, light inference NC2d towards the end of Phase 1, some prediction interwoven too

Fluency

Accuracy > automaticity > Prosody (phrasing, intonation, pace, dramatic expression)

Metacognitive

- Monitoring use of ‘click or clunk’,
- clarifying
- visualizing
- self-questioning

Examples of independent tasks in Phase 1

- Retrieve and record basic facts from pages.
- Literal comprehension questions – who, what, where, when
- Sketch a diagram and label with key tier 2/3 vocabulary taught in the lesson.
- Fill in sentence stems using key vocabulary.

Progression of metacognition, fluency skills and comprehension domains in Phase 2

Comprehension

- NC2d – inference: character feelings, motivations, cause and effect, predictive inference, light thematic inference.
- NC2f – authorial intent: word choice, sentence structure, figurative language, structural analysis
- NC2c – Summarising – Cross-page connections
- NC2a – Vocabulary – embedded and continually exercised.
- NC2b – retrieval – locating evidence to support answers

Examples of Independent activities in Phase 2

- Character inference questions using stems: I infer _____ because (evidence)
- Authorial intent stems: The author used _____ because _____.
- Character feelings inference table with evidence column.
- Identify and explain a simile or other figurative language choice and the effect on the audience.
- Compare characters using venn diagram and evidence.
- Predictions with justification from the text
- Cross-page evidence hunt – finding examples of a theme or trait across pages.

Metacognition

- Self-questioning, monitoring, clarifying, predicting, and monitoring the depth of understanding

Fluency

- Prosodic focus: intonation and expression matches meaning of the text
- Pacing
- All Phase 1 fluency embedded – fluency demonstrates and supports comprehension

Progression of metacognition, fluency skills and comprehension domains in Phase 3

Independent activities

- Trace character arcs on a timeline using quotes and evidence.
- Whole text summary identifying key themes
- Comparison charts: beginning vs end for setting/character/mood
- Write in the author's style using identified techniques.
- Sentences responding to the overarching idea of a text (what is it really about)
- Metacognitive reflection: how has my understanding of _____ changed?
- Connecting evidence from different pages
- Reviewing the book using justification

Key domains

- NC2c – summarising: whole text, main ideas, character arcs, thematic statements
- NC2d – Inference: Thematic /global inference,
- NC2f – Authorial intent: whole text structural analysis, character choice
- Extended writing in the style of the author (read/write connection)
- Metacognition
- Monitoring for patterns across the text
- Evaluation: What's the most significant...
- Metacognition on learning processes – what strategy helped me...
- Metacognitive transfer: how will I use this in the next text?
- Fluency
- Performance reading: fluency embedded
- Rehearsed performances

Assessment

Throughout this model there is ample opportunity for assessment. Daily formative assessment is crucial and can be undertaken through listening to the quality of pupil's dialogue in scaffolded oracy activities and through their responses in daily independent tasks. Throughout each six-week unit, all reading domains which appear in the National Curriculum are covered in depth. Pupils' holistic comprehension of the text can be accurately assessed in Phase 3 as the task design is such that pupils require a deep understanding of plot and character to answer prompts effectively.

Adaptation

This model has been constructed with Pearson and Gallagher's teachings on the gradual release of scaffolding and the sentence stems in phases 1 and 2 make tasks highly accessible without compromising task difficulty and complexity. Cognitive load is managed effectively throughout; as pupil's strengthen schema, scaffolding is withdrawn. For pupils, who require adaptations continually throughout the unit, scaffolding can be maintained throughout the unit. Additionally, pre-teaching vocabulary will reduce cognitive load in lesson for pupils who require this.

Conclusion

The phases I have outlined here are a synthesis of existing research, all of which is complementary and has enabled me to create this framework for teaching reading according to the needs of the National Curriculum, but also by following the evidence. Phase 1 builds the text base and ensures the pupils have exercised the crucial skills needed to retrieve evidence later. Phase 2 allows pupils to engage with the text in a closer, deeper manner and utilise skills and techniques not possible without the solid text base established in Phase 1. Phase 3 is a demonstration of understanding. It is a reflection of the overarching themes, character journeys and the pupil's own reading journey. It is vital that the pupils are able to synthesise all the knowledge they have gained throughout the unit. They can see the bigger picture and truly understand the author's intentions and vision.

In the classroom, I have already seen the impact of this framework on my pupils. They are able to retain vocabulary far more effectively and are more accurate in their inferential thinking. Additionally, they are approaching the text in more complex and meaningful ways and exploring this in a great variety of written explanations and oral discussions. While more data and evidence need to be collected from a variety of settings, environments and cohorts, the framework utilises highly regarded research in a logical way and engages with research, OFSTED recommendations and metacognitive approaches in a way in which very few reading schemes do. This approach is deliberately evidenced and, I believe, genuinely engaging for pupils. Teachers have the freedom to select their own high-quality texts and draw the independent activities from the rich content of the pages rather than mechanically answering lists of questions arbitrarily. This is a text – based, fluid and researched approach which I believe pupils can truly benefit from. Pupils deserve the

opportunity to become excellent readers and to love books. I believe this approach can achieve this.

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